

Spectrophotometric Determination of Beryllium(II) and Mercury(II) with *N*-(4-Methylphenyl)-3-oxobutanamide

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Manuscript received 22 February 1996, revised 30 August 1996, accepted 20 September 1996

β -Diketones are well known for their analytical use¹. Das reported benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide¹ for spectrophotometric determination of Be^{II}, and cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide² for Hg^{II} and Be^{II}. The present work describes *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-3-oxobutanamide, a β -diketo compound, as a reagent for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of Be^{II} and Hg^{II}.

Results and Discussion

The optical characteristics and quantitative results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—OPTIMUM OPERATING CONDITIONS USING ONE VARIABLE AT A TIME AND OPTICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Operating condition :	Be ^{II}	Hg ^{II}
Absorption band (nm)	270–370	290–370
pH-range (NH ₄ OH)	8.5–9.6	7.6–9.8
Min. quantities of reagent (mg)	40	50
Solvent	CHCl ₃	CHCl ₃
No. of extraction	1	1
Stability of absorbance (h)	8	30
Optical characteristics :		
Linear dynamic range ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$)	0.5–16.0	2.0–50.0
Optimum photometric range ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$)	2.2–7.0	7.5–23.9
Sandell's sensitivity	0.01	0.034
Linear least-square method applied on concentration vs absorbance data shows		
(i) Slope	0.096	0.03
(ii) Extinction coefficient ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	865.2	6017.7
% Rel. std. deviation	± 1.3	± 1.36
Stoichiometry (M : L; elemental analysis)	1 : 2	1 : 2

Beryllium(II) (90 μg) could be determined in the presence of 0.4 mg of each of AsO₄³⁻, WO₄²⁻, MoO₄²⁻, BO₃³⁻ and SCN⁻. The interference due to presence of 0.4 mg of Fe^{III}, Cr^{III}, Al^{III}, As^{III}; 0.9 mg of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and VO^{II} could be avoided by masking them with 400 mg disodium EDTA. Amount of 0.4 mg TiO^{II} and UO₂^{II} did not interfere in presence of 250 mg tartaric acid. Mercury(II) (200 μg) could be determined in presence of 5 mg of each of Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Be^{II}, Mn^{II}, Pb^{II}, and 3 mg of each of Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III} using 200 mg citric acid as a masking agent. The determination could be carried out in presence of 5 mg of each of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ca^{II},

Mg^{II}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, 3 mg of Sn^{II}, UO₂^{II} and 2 mg of Th^{IV}, Zr^{IV} after prior masking of these ions with 200 mg tartaric acid. Presence of 2 mg each of AsO₄³⁻, Mo₇O₂₄⁶⁻, SCN⁻ and F⁻ had no adverse effect on the determination of mercury(II).

Experimental

Spectral measurements were done by a Beckman D.B.G. spectrophotometer. An Elico LI-IOT pH meter was used.

N-(4-Methylphenyl)-3-oxobutanamide was synthesised³ and the reagent solutions (2.0–4.5%) were prepared in 40% ethanol. Aqueous solutions of hydrated beryllium sulphate (A.R.) and mercuric chloride (A.R.) were prepared and acidified with H₂SO₄ and HCl respectively.

Extraction procedure : A known amount of the standard solution containing 45–135 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Be was diluted to 20 ml and a solution of *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-3-oxobutanamide (2.0%; 2 ml) was added and its pH was adjusted to 8.5–9.6 with 2.0 *N* NH₄OH. The mixture was then shaken for 5 min and the resulting complex was extracted with chloroform (2 \times 5 ml). The combined extract was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and its absorbance was measured at 290 nm against the reagent blank.

An aliquot of the standard mercury solution (50.0–131.35 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was diluted to 15 ml, warmed to $\sim 40^\circ$ and the reagent solution (4.5%; 1 ml) was added to it. pH was adjusted to 7.6–9.8 with 1.0 *N* NH₄OH. The mixture was shaken for 5 min and the resulting complex was extracted with chloroform as described above.

The ore sample (200 mg) was fused with potassium hydrogen fluoride in a platinum crucible. The fused mass was then cooled, treated with H₂SO₄ and heated to fume to remove fluoride. The mass was taken in 1.5 *M* H₂SO₄, boiled and filtered. The volume of the filtrate was made upto 500 ml. A 10 ml portion of this solution was made up to 25 ml. A 2 ml portion of the final solution was treated as described earlier after adding disodium salt of EDTA (400 mg). The results are as follows : BeO and Be by standard method², 18.98 and 6.84% respectively; those by the present method, 18.87, 19.05 and 6.80, 6.86 respectively.

References

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